

Assessment of the effectiveness of allergic rhinitis medications using a target trial emulation approach based on mobile health data

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Methods

Study design

We performed a study using direct patient data from the MASK-air[®] app, assessing participants with self-reported AR. We evaluated participants who answered the MASK-air[®] monitoring questionnaire, having reported symptoms before and after taking an oral antihistamine (OAH), an intranasal corticosteroid (INCS), or a fixed combination of an intranasal antihistamine (INAH) + INCS. We compared these medication classes on changes in symptoms as assessed through visual analogue scales (VAS). In addition, we evaluated whether having asthma influenced the effect of the different medication classes on AR symptoms. In order to minimise the impact of confounding, we used a target trial emulation framework.

Settings and participants

We included MASK-air[®] users (i) aged between 16 and 75 years old (or more than 13 years in countries where the age of digital consent is lower) and (ii) who had self-reported AR. Data were collected from January 1, 2015, to December 31, 2024. To be included in this analysis, patients must have answered the MASK-air[®] daily monitoring questionnaire twice in a 24-hour period: the first time before taking any medication and the second after taking OAH, INCS, or INAH+INCS in monotherapy. Measurements with less than 60 minutes of interval were excluded.

Our analysis focused on symptom changes observed within a 24-hour period following medication use. This specific timeframe was chosen for three main reasons. Firstly, this timeframe is clinically relevant for evaluating acute symptom control, which is a primary goal for patients managing their AR daily. Secondly, the assessed medications - OAH, INCS, and INAH + INCS - typically provide symptomatic relief for approximately 24 hours[12]. This period therefore directly reflects the intended acute clinical effectiveness of a single medication intake. Thirdly, the design of the MASK-air[®] app, which encourages daily symptom and medication logging, naturally lends itself to capturing pre- and post-treatment observations within a 24-hour cycle.

Ethics

MASK-air[®] has a *Conformité Européenne* 1 (CE1) marking[10]. It has additionally been classified as a Medical Device Regulation (MDR) Class IIa[10]. All data are introduced by users anonymously, and geolocation-related data are then “masked” using k-anonymity for added privacy[13]. Approval from an independent review board was not required for this study because (i) the use of MASK-air[®] data for research purposes had already been approved by an independent

review board (Köln-Bonn, Germany; reference number 17–069)[14], (ii) all data were anonymised prior to the study, and (iii) users consented to the analysis of their data for research purposes in the terms of use.

Data sources and variables

MASK-air[®] comprises a daily monitoring questionnaire, including four VAS on a scale from 0 to 100 (higher values denote more severe symptoms) (Supplementary Table 1). In addition, the MASK-air[®] daily monitoring questionnaire allows users to log their daily medication through a country-specific scroll list. To better reflect patient experiences, monotherapy was defined as days when only a single formulation was reported, even if it contained multiple active ingredients (fixed combinations of INAH+INCS were considered as monotherapy). Figure 1 depicts the data collection process considered for this study.

Sample size

We analysed data from all users who met the eligibility criteria and had valid data. No sample size calculation was conducted.

Target Trial Emulation

We compared post-medication VAS over a maximum period of one day after patients had used OAH, INCS, or INAH+INCS. In order to minimise design-related biases and to better account for confounding, we used the target trial framework defined by Hernán et al. [15, 16] (Table 1). Since (i) we are assessing a 24-hour window period, and (ii) the interventions tested do not vary with time along that period (i.e., we are considering a single intervention with no time-varying component), we designed a target trial for a time-fixed treatment corresponding to a point intervention.

To identify potential confounders that we would need to adjust for, we built a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) (Figure 2). We assumed that the use of AR medication in a certain day – i.e., both the fact that patient uses medication, and the class of medication used – is influenced by (i) AR severity (i.e., whether the patient has a milder or a more severe form of the disease) and (ii) disease variability (the intensity of symptoms can vary throughout the year, being influenced by aspects such as pollen levels). The ARIA score was considered a variable indicative of AR severity. The ARIA score has been previously shown to correlate with quality of life in previous works[17], and is determined by summing the presence of AR-related sleep disturbances, impairment in work or school performance, daily activity limitations, or bothersome symptoms[17]. Each of these

categories is scored as either 1 (present) or 0 (absent), so that the ARIA score ranges between 0 and 4. Pre-medication VAS scores were considered to inform on the intensity of symptoms before medication use.

Statistical analysis

In the daily monitoring questionnaire, it is mandatory to respond to all questions, with data being recorded in the dataset only after questionnaire completion. This design ensures that there is no missing data within each questionnaire.

Categorical variables were described using absolute and relative frequencies, while continuous variables were summarized using medians and interquartile ranges (IQRs).

We built mixed-effects regression models[18] to compare the following pairs of treatments: (i) INCS vs. OAH, (ii) INAH+INCS vs. OAH, and (iii) INCS vs. INAH+INCS. For each pair of treatments, we compared mean differences in global allergy symptoms (“VAS global”), nasal symptoms (“VAS nose”), ocular symptoms (“VAS eye”), and asthma symptoms (“VAS asthma”).

To adjust for confounding and ensure comparability across treatment groups, we used an inverse probability of treatment weighting (IPTW) based approach[19]. In detail, for each comparison, we started by building mixed-effects logistic regression models to compute the probability of each patient having received one treatment over the other (“propensity scores”). In these models, the dependent variable was the medication class used, and the independent variables were the pre-medication VAS scores, age, gender, occurrence of comorbid self-reported asthma, and the ARIA score. In addition, we set the patient and the month of the year as random-effects (i.e., we clustered observations by patient and by month of the year). Stabilized IPTW were then computed from the posterior predictive distributions of the propensity scores.

Finally, treatment effects were estimated using Bayesian mixed-effects linear regression models[20–23] where the dependent variable was post-treatment VAS scores, and the treatment received was the independent variable. The reported “VAS difference” values represent the Average Treatment Effect (ATE), which are the mean differences in post-medication VAS scores between the compared treatment groups, adjusted for confounding through the IPTW approach. The computed IPTW were used to weigh observations, and we set the patient and the month of the year as random-effects.

We performed an additional analysis, adding an interaction term for asthma in our models. This allowed for differential estimation of treatment effects across the subgroups of patients with and without asthma.

All analyses were performed using the software R, version 4.4.2, with analyses being implemented using the brms package with four Markov chains and 2000 iterations per chain. We used weakly informative priors for the model parameters, specifically a normal distribution with mean 0 and standard deviation 10 for the regression coefficients and a half-Cauchy distribution with scale 2.5 for the standard deviation of the random effects. Treatment effect estimates were summarized using Bayesian posterior means and 95% credible intervals (CrIs). Additionally, we reported the proportion of posterior samples favouring a specific treatment direction (i.e., the probability of one treatment being more effective than the other in improving VAS values).

Assumptions checking

Prior to model fitting, we visually inspected diagnostic plots for the Bayesian mixed-effects linear regression models to assess assumptions such as linearity and homoscedasticity. Given the nature of our real-world data, strict normality of residuals was not assumed, and our Bayesian approach with weakly informative priors is robust to minor deviations from normality. For the logistic regression models, we assessed the overall fit.

Following the application of IPTW, we evaluated covariate balance across treatment groups. Standardized mean differences (SMDs) were calculated for all covariates included in the propensity score models (pre-medication VAS scores, age, gender, occurrence of comorbid self-reported asthma, and ARIA score) to ensure that the weighted groups were comparable. We confirmed that most SMDs were below the conventional threshold of 0.1, indicating adequate balance was achieved and maintained after weighting, thus minimizing confounding bias. Supplementary Figure 1 depicts the covariate balance pre- and post-IPTW for VAS Global. A similar balance distribution was observed for VAS Asthma, VAS Eye, and VAS Nose.

Convergence of the Bayesian mixed-effects models was assessed using standard diagnostics. We confirmed that all R-hat values were close to 1, indicating good convergence of the Markov chains. Trace plots were visually inspected for proper mixing, and effective sample sizes were monitored to ensure sufficient sampling from the posterior distributions. All models demonstrated satisfactory convergence, except for the models comparing single medication strategies against co-medication or no treatment, which showed a lack of convergence due to insufficient data for those comparisons and thus were not considered.

Results

Characteristics of the assessed sample

The study analysed 648 days in which MASK-air[®] users answered twice to the daily monitoring questionnaire. Most days (n=400) were reported by females, and the median age of participants was 37 years (IQR: 23) (Table 2). The distribution of days per country is displayed in Supplementary Table 2. Self-reported asthma was present in 37·8% of the participants. The median time between the second and the first responses to the daily monitoring questionnaire was of 480 minutes (IQR=568·2). Most days involved the use of OAH (64·2%), followed by INCS (25·5%) and INAH+INCS (10·3%; only days with azelastine-fluticasone were included due to lack of data for olopatadine-mometasone). Supplementary Table 3 displays the pre-medication median VAS levels and ARIA scores per medication class. The time difference between the first and second reports was 336 minutes for INAH+INCS, 462 minutes for OAH, and 569 minutes for INCS (Supplementary Table 3).

There was an overall decrease in median values of VASs when comparing the second *versus* the first registration of the daily monitoring questionnaire. For VAS global, the median values were of 27 (IQR=37) for the first measurement compared to 18 (IQR=37) for the second measurement. For VAS eye, these values were 11 (IQR=31) versus 7 (IQR=23), and for VAS nose 28 (IQR=40) versus 21 (IQR=36). Median VAS asthma had the same value for the entire study population (2) at the first and second measurements, although it differed significantly in patients who self-reported as having asthma (first measurement: 14 (IQR=31); second measurement: 10 (IQR=25), respectively).

Comparison of treatment responses in VAS scores

Global symptoms

INAH+INCS and INCS were more effective than OAH in reducing VAS Global scores, particularly in patients without asthma (Table 3). INCS resulted in a decrease of 4·25 points of VAS compared to OAH (95%CrI=-6·69,-1·15, 99·3% probability of INCS being more effective). This average reduction was of -3·50 points in patients with asthma (95%CrI=-7·94,-0·39, 96·4%) compared to -5·06 in those without asthma (95%CrI=-8·27,-1·54, 99·2%). INAH+INCS were also associated with a substantial reduction in VAS global compared to OAH (-7·27; 95%CrI=-10·30,-4·07, >99·9%), with this decrease being less pronounced in participants with asthma (-3·25; 95%CrI=9·53,2·52, 88·6%) than in those without asthma (-10·0; 95%CrI=-14·2,-6·91, >99·9%). The comparison between INAH+INCS and INCS showed variable effects depending

on asthma status. When considering the overall population, both INAH+INCS and INCSN had rather identical effects (0.62; 95%CrI=-2.59,1.20, 74.1%). Among participants with asthma, INAH+INCS were associated with a greater reduction in VAS scores (-6.64; 95%CrI=-12.0,-0.17, 97.7%) compared to INCS alone, whereas in participants without asthma, the combination resulted in higher VAS scores than INCS (5.09; 95%CrI=-5.39,13.3, 15.5%).

Nasal symptoms

For VAS Nose, INCS was also more effective than OAH, with the effect size being similar in asthma participants (-6.86; 95%CrI=-10.0,-3.07, >99.9%) and non-asthma participants (-6.69; 95%CrI=-9.51,-3.94, 99.9%) (Table 3). While INAH+INCS and OAH showed a negligible overall difference (0.01; 95%CrI=-3.40,3.32, 51.2%), INAH+INCS was significantly more effective in non-asthma participants (-9.13; 95%CrI=-13.3,-6.09, 99.9%). However, in asthma participants, OAH was significantly more effective (10.9; 95%CrI=1.74,18.5, 0.02%). Adding INAH to INCS provided minimal additional benefit (-0.46; 95%CrI=-1.92,1.00, 75.2%).

Ocular symptoms

For VAS eye, both INCS and INAH+INCS were associated with a larger effect than OAH (Table 3). INCS was associated with an improvement of 5.29 points in patients with asthma (95%CrI=-8.61,-0.21, 97.8%) compared to -4.32 in those without asthma (95%CrI=-8.76,-0.82, 99.0%). INAH+INCS demonstrated a larger reduction of VAS eye levels in non-asthma participants (-6.93; 95%CrI=-9.13,-3.75, >99.9%) than in asthma participants (-1.74; 95%CrI=-7.93,5.11, 72.8%). The comparison between INAH+INCS and INCS was associated with a small difference (-1.30; 95%CrI=-3.36,1.05, 89.0%).

Asthma

For VAS Asthma, INCS and OAH showed a minimal overall difference (-0.29; 95%CrI=-2.41,1.04, 61.3%). INAH+INCS was associated with an improvement in VAS asthma compared to INCS (-2.39; 95%CrI=-3.20,-1.56, >99.9%) and OAH (-5.64; 95%CrI=-11.9,1.97, 94.7%) (Table 3). The effect of INAH+INCS compared to OAH was less pronounced in non-asthma participants (-3.13; 95%CrI=4.03,0.92, 99.8%) compared to asthma participants (-6.04; 95%CrI=-17.8,7.88, 82.9%).

Figures

Figure 1. Data collection methodology diagram

GDPR: general data protection regulation; RCT: Randomised Clinical Trial.

Figure 2. Directed acyclic graph representing the relationships between (i) medication use, (ii) Symptoms reported previously and after medication use, and (iii) potential confounders

ARIA – Allergic Rhinitis and Its Impact on Asthma.

Tables

Table 1. Summary of the protocol of a target trial comparing different medications on changes in rhinitis symptoms.

Component	Hypothetical pragmatic randomised trial	Target Trial Emulation
Eligibility criteria	Patients self-reporting as diagnosed with AR, with age between 16 and 75 years, or younger (no less than 13 years) if with parental consent.	Participants must meet the following criteria: same as hypothetical trial And Registration of two records in the daily monitoring questionnaire of the MASK-air [®] app (before and after taking AR medication).
Treatment strategies	One of these three classes: 1. Oral antihistamines; 2. Intranasal corticosteroids; 3. Fixed combinations of intranasal antihistamines + intranasal corticosteroids.	Same as the hypothetical trial
Assignment Procedures	Participants are randomly assigned to a strategy at baseline.	Randomization was conditional on baseline severity, pre-treatment symptoms, age, sex, and self-reported asthma in order to enhance comparability between groups.
Follow-up period	24-hour window-period	Same as the hypothetical trial
Primary outcome	Post-medication symptoms reported through visual analogue scales (after versus before taking the medication).	Same as the hypothetical trial.
Causal contrast	Per protocol effect	Observational analogue of the per protocol effect

AR – Allergic rhinitis.

Table 2. Characteristics of observations included in this study.

Variable	Assessed sample (N=648)
Age, median (IQR, range)	37 (23)
Gender, n (%)	
Male	248 (38.2)
Female	400 (61.8)
European country, n (%)	536 (82.7)
ARIA score, n (%)	
0	204 (31.5)
1	95 (14.7)
2	101 (15.6)
3	125 (19.3)
4	123 (19.0)
Time difference between 1 st and 2 nd measurements (minutes), median (IQR)	480.0 (568.2)
Medication scheme, n (%)	
OAH	416 (64.2)
INCS	165 (25.5)
INAH+INCS	67 (10.3)
Self-reported asthma, n (%)	245 (37.8)
Medication scheme, n (%)	
OAH	166 (44.4)
INCS	55 (32.1)
INAH+INCS	24 (36.3)
Global allergy symptoms	
VAS Global (1 st measurement), median (IQR)	27 (37)
VAS Global (2 nd measurement), median (IQR)	18 (37)
Ocular Symptoms	
VAS Eye (1 st measurement), median (IQR)	11 (31)
VAS Eye (2 nd measurement), median (IQR)	7 (23)
Nasal Symptoms	
VAS Nose (1 st measurement), median (IQR)	28 (40)
VAS Nose (2 nd measurement), median (IQR)	21 (36)
Asthma Symptoms	
VAS Asthma (1 st measurement), median (IQR)	2 (16)
VAS Asthma (2 nd measurement), median (IQR)	2 (12)

INAH + INCS – Intranasal antihistamine + intranasal corticosteroids combination; INCS – Intranasal corticosteroids; IQR – Interquartile range; OAH – Oral antihistamines; VAS – Visual Analogue Score.

Table 3. Adjusted changes in VAS Global, Eye, Nose, and Asthma scores when comparing treatment categories.

Comparison	Difference in VAS [95% Credible Interval], probability of intervention being more effective than comparison (%)		
	All Participants	Participants with asthma	Participants without asthma
VAS Global			
INCS vs. OAH	-4.25 [-6.69, -1.15], 99.3	-3.50 [-7.94, -0.39], 96.4	-5.06 [-8.27, -1.54], 99.2
INAH + INCS vs. INCS	0.62 [-2.59, 1.20], 74.1	-6.64 [-12.0, -0.17], 97.7	5.09 [-5.39, 13.3], 15.5
INAH + INCS vs. OAH	-7.27 [-10.30, -4.07], >99.9	-3.25 [-9.53, 2.52], 88.6	-10.0 [-14.2, -6.91], >99.9
VAS Eye			
INCS vs. OAH	-4.99 [-7.22, -2.05], 99.6	-5.29 [-8.61, -0.21], 97.8	-4.32 [-8.76, -0.82], 99.0
INAH + INCS vs. INCS	-1.30 [-3.36, 1.05], 89.0	-0.25 [-7.23, 9.20], 60.0	0.01 [-8.58, 6.88], 55.6
INAH + INCS vs. OAH	-5.90 [-9.69, -2.41], 99.6	-1.74 [-7.93, 5.11], 72.8	-6.93 [-9.13, -3.75], >99.9
VAS Nose			
INCS vs. OAH	-6.37 [-8.19, -4.50], >99.9	-6.86 [-10.0, -3.07], >99.9	-6.69 [-9.51, -3.94], 99.9
INAH + INCS vs. INCS	-0.46 [-1.92, 1.00], 75.2	-0.10 [-10.8, 10.6], 54.5	0.05 [-11.2, 6.64], 38.7
INAH + INCS vs. OAH	0.01 [-3.40, 3.32], 51.2	10.9, [1.74, 18.5], 0.02	-9.13 [-13.3, -6.09], 99.9
VAS Asthma			
INCS vs. OAH	-0.29 [-2.41, 1.04], 61.3	0.53 [-1.87, 3.99], 40.4	-0.90 [-2.06, 0.05], 97.1
INAH + INCS vs. INCS	-2.39 [-3.20, -1.56], >99.9	-4.11 [-8.01, 2.50], 91.8	0.40 [0.26, 0.51], <0.01
INAH + INCS vs. OAH	-5.64 [-11.9, 1.97], 94.7	-6.04 [-17.8, 7.88], 82.9	-3.13 [-4.03, 0.92], 99.8

INAH + INCS – Intranasal antihistamine + intranasal corticosteroids combination; INCS – Intranasal corticosteroids; OAH – Oral Antihistamines; VAS – Visual Analogue Scale.

Supplementary Material

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table 1. Visual analogue scales (VASs) used for daily monitoring the impact of allergic rhinitis and asthma symptoms in MASK-air[®]

VAS	Question
VAS Global Allergy Symptoms	Overall, how much are your allergic symptoms bothering you today?
VAS Nose	How much are your nose symptoms bothering you today?
VAS Eyes	How much are your eye symptoms bothering you today?
VAS Asthma	How much are your asthma symptoms bothering you today?

Supplementary Table 2. Frequency of included days per country

Country	<i>N</i> pairs (n, %)
Argentina	21 (3.2)
Australia	4 (0.6)
Austria	14 (2.2)
Belgium	2 (0.3)
Brazil	33 (5.1)
Canada	2 (0.3)
Czech Republic	10 (1.5)
Denmark	1 (0.2)
Ecuador	5 (0.8)
Finland	3 (0.5)
France	51 (7.9)
Germany	138 (21.2)
Great Britain	6 (0.9)
Greece	32 (4.9)
Hungary	15 (2.3)
Italy	49 (7.6)
Japan	2 (0.3)
Lithuania	75 (11.6)
Mexico	39 (6.0)
Netherlands	7 (1.1)
Poland	36 (5.6)
Portugal	45 (6.9)
Slovenia	6 (0.9)
Spain	33 (5.1)
Sweden	1 (0.2)
Switzerland	11 (1.7)
Turkey	6 (0.9)
Ukraine	1 (0.2)

Supplementary Table 3. Distribution of ARIA score of the observations included in this study, aggregated according to medication scheme

Variable	Medication scheme			Effect size		
	OAH	INCS	INAH+INCS	OAH vs INCS	OAH vs INAH+INCS	INCS vs INAH+INCS
ARIA score, n (%)						
0	122 (29)	59 (36)	23 (34)	0.14	0.11	0.03
1	55 (13)	26 (16)	14 (21)	0.07	0.21	0.13
2	65 (16)	27 (16)	9 (13)	0.02	0.06	0.08
3	96 (23)	24 (15)	5 (7)	0.22	0.45	0.23
4	78 (19)	29 (18)	16 (24)	0.03	0.12	0.16
Pre-medication scores						
VAS Global, median (IQR)	26 (38)	27 (37)	28 (35)	0.04	0.08	0.04
VAS Eye, median (IQR)	13 (32)	9 (28)	8 (20)	0.24	0.32	0.08
VAS Nose, median (IQR)	28 (41)	29 (35)	25 (39)	0.04	0.12	0.16
VAS Asthma, median (IQR)						
Asthma patients	14 (24)	19 (41)	13 (16)	0.30	0.06	0.25
Non-asthma patients	0 (2)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0	0	0
Time period between measurements (minutes), median (IQR)	462 (571)	569 (571)	336 (629)	0.25	0.33	0.58

INAH + INCS – Intranasal antihistamine + intranasal corticosteroids combination; INCS – Intranasal corticosteroids; IQR – Interquartile range; MAD - median absolute deviation; OAH – Oral antihistamines; VAS – Visual Analogue Score.

Supplementary figure 1. Covariance balance before and after inverse probability treatment weighting (IPTW) for models analysing visual analogue scale on global allergy symptoms (“VAS global”). Absolute differences <0.10 indicate good covariate balance

Covariate Balance Before and After IPTW

A. OAH vs INCS

B. INCS vs INCS+INAH

C. OAH vs INCS+INAH

INAH=Intranasal antihistamines; INCS=Intranasal corticosteroids; OAH=Oral antihistamines